

Additional file 2. Results of multiple linear regression models with control for confounding variables

	NHS vs. SMC	NHS vs. MCI	NHS vs. AD	AD vs. SMC	AD vs. MCI	MCI vs. SMC
IL-1 α	0.19 (-0.25 to 0.63) <i>p</i> =0.39	-0.21 (-0.68 to 0.24) <i>p</i> =0.35	9.17 (1.62 to 16.7) <i>p</i> =0.018	7.9 (-1.81 to 17.6) <i>p</i> =0.11	9.97 (-0.69 to 20.6) <i>p</i> =0.06	-0.13 (-0.61 to 0.34) <i>p</i> =0.58
IL-1 β	-0.15 (-1.1 to 0.8) <i>p</i> =0.75	-0.4 (-1.58 to 0.59) <i>p</i> =0.37	7.9 (1.63 to 14.3) <i>p</i> =0.014	8.1 (0.16 to 16.1) <i>p</i> =0.046	11.1 (2.51 to 19.7) <i>p</i> =0.012	0.23 (-0.34 to 0.8) <i>p</i> =0.42
IL-1Ra	-25.9 (-52.5 to 0.6) <i>p</i> =0.056	-3.7 (-33.9 to 26.5) <i>p</i> =0.8	116.9 (0.34 to 237.3) <i>p</i> =0.049	98.3 (-51.8 to 248.5) <i>p</i> =0.19	125.3 (-42.2 to 293.3) <i>p</i> =0.14	40.9 (7.6 to 74.2) <i>p</i> =0.016
IL-18	-39.4 (-69.4 to -9.3) <i>p</i> =0.01	16.7 (-22.2 to 55.7) <i>p</i> =0.39	-48.6 (-206.8 to 109.5) <i>p</i> =0.54	-16.1 (-210.2 to 178.1) <i>p</i> =0.87	-40.6 (-259.9 to 178.7) <i>p</i> =0.71	52.8 (8.8 to 96.8) <i>p</i> =0.019
IL-33	-0.39 (-1.09 to 0.29) <i>p</i> =0.26	-0.60 (-1.38 to 0.17) <i>p</i> =0.12	7.5 (2.2 to 12.9) <i>p</i> =0.006	6.9 (0.21 to 13.6) <i>p</i> =0.043	9.1 (1.8 to 16.4) <i>p</i> =0.014	0.25 (-0.22 to 0.741) <i>p</i> =0.29
sIL-1R1	-193.4 (-266.5 to -120.4) <i>p</i> <0.001	-58.2 (-155.2 to 38.82) <i>p</i> =0.23	268.9 (68.41 to -469.58) <i>p</i> =0.009	471.2 (242.1 to 700.3) <i>p</i> <0.001	327.2 (31.57 to 622.9) <i>p</i> =0.03	81.65 (-36.6 to 199.9) <i>p</i> =0.173
sIL-1R2	-812.8 (-1383.2 to -242.4) <i>p</i> =0.006	3402.4 (2567.4 to 4237.4) <i>p</i> <0.001	-1337.8 (-2733.4 to 57.8) <i>p</i> =0.06	212.5 (-1061.0 to 1486.1) <i>p</i> =0.74	-4148.5 (-6065.7 to -2231) <i>p</i> <0.001	4098.8 (3154.7 to 5042.9) <i>p</i> <0.001
sIL-1R3	1526.13 (759.1 to 2293.0) <i>p</i> <0.001	-255.9 (-1122.8 to 610.9) <i>p</i> =0.56	1765.6 (180.85 to 3350.5) <i>p</i> =0.029	607.3 (-1258.0 to 2472.6) <i>p</i> =0.52	2306.2 (435.3 to 4177.3) <i>p</i> =0.016	-947.8 (-1932.6 to 36.8) <i>p</i> =0.059
sIL-1R4	-53.0 (-946.5 to 840.4) <i>p</i> =0.9	-594.0 (-1627.4 to 439.4) <i>p</i> =0.25	3761.7 (422.1 to 7101.4) <i>p</i> =0.028	4780.1 (658.9 to 8901.3) <i>p</i> =0.023	5005.9 (379.3 to 9632.6) <i>p</i> =0.034	114.2 (-1276.0 to 1504.5) <i>p</i> =0.87
IL-18BP	-3848.2 (-4831.3 to -2865) <i>p</i> <0.001	-4742.6 (-5906 to -3759.4) <i>p</i> <0.001	6792.1 (2938.5 to 10645.5) <i>p</i> =0.001	12377.6 (7917.1 to 16838) <i>p</i> <0.001	13298.1 (8389.8 to 18206) <i>p</i> <0.001	109.79 (-828.7 to 1048.3) <i>p</i> =0.81
free IL-18	10.99 (-4.79 to 26.79) <i>p</i> =0.17	48.98 (29.74 to 68.2) <i>p</i> <0.001	-47.0 (-110.64 to 16.45) <i>p</i> =0.14	-69.5 (-148.0 to 9.03) <i>p</i> =0.082	-88.73 (-177.0 to -0.39) <i>p</i> =0.049	33.0 (7.49 to 58.56) <i>p</i> =0.012

Values are β coefficients (95% confidence intervals) and *p* values.

AD, Alzheimer's disease; MCI, mild cognitive impairment; NHS, normal healthy subjects; SMC, subjective memory complaint.